

DESIGN AND SELECTION OF MATERIAL AND PROCESS FOR A FOLDING CHAIR TO BE USED BY LOCAL SEWING WORKERS USING HOUSE OF QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

The chair has been in use since the beginning of civilization. Different special purpose chairs are available depending on the need of the user or customer. One of the special purpose chairs is folding chair, it is a type of a chair which can be folded and unfolded whenever required. In this study, a relationship between customer requirements and engineering characteristics of a folding chair used by seamstresses working from their home have been analysed using house of quality. To develop a house of quality, a survey has been carried out to find out the important customer requirements. A relationship between requirements and different engineering qualities of a foldable chair is developed. Using house of quality, the most important engineering qualities of a folding chair have been found. It is found that a chair should have easy folding and unfolding mechanism. It should also have lower weight. These two engineering qualities make a folding chair convenient to use. Based on the inputs taken from the HoQ, a design for a folding chair has been prepared which has three major components. From the Ashby's method of material and manufacturing process selection, it was found that aluminium alloy is the most suitable material and die casting is the most suitable manufacturing process.

Keywords: House of Quality, Material selection, Customer Requirements

Introduction

Chair is the one of the most common part of our daily life. We use chair for doing different work while sitting on it. Depending on the work we are doing, we have different types of chair which are permanent chair, folding or adjustable chair, wheelchair and multi-purpose chair. Permanent chairs are used when we have larger space available in the room and when we don't need to go here and there frequently in the room. Folding chairs are used when we have less

area available in our room. So, that we can fold and unfold the chair whenever required. Wheel chairs have wheels at the end of its legs. It is mainly used in the hospital for differently-abled people. However, it is also used by common people when there is a requirement for going here and there frequently in the room. Multi-purpose chair are designed based on the customer's requirements.

Folding Chairs or adjustable chairs are used where permanent sitting is not practical or when the larger free space is not available in the room. They can be easily moved or transported and stored. They are used in places like schools, hospitals, funerals, religious services, and private parties at home. Folding chairs have been in use for centuries. Different examples have been found in different civilizations like Romans, Greeks and Egypt. They were using simple 'X' shaped folding chair. A folding chair of around 1400s BC has been found from Guldhoj (Gold hills) in Jutland, Denmark [1]. This is the only preserved wooden folding chair from Bronze era in Europe. The use of folding chairs became wide spread in the middle ages when churches started using them for their prayer meetings. We have earliest patented folding chair by John Cram in 1855 [2]. After that countless other patents have been filed across the world. After the World War II, in 1947, Fredric Arnold designed a foldable aluminium framed chair for mass production [3]. After a decade, Fredric Arnold Company based in Brooklyn was selling 14000 chairs per day. The chair had arm rest, and the seat and back were made up of fabric material.

Literature Review

Chen (2013) has studied the applied quality function deployment to find out the demand of customers for plastic folding chair [4]. He studied the five major demands of customers which are comfort, aesthetics, safety, convenience and environmental protection using house of quality function. He concluded that among the customer demands: taking consideration of ergonomics (6.5%), non-pinching during use (6.7%) and parts unlikely to fall off (6.8%) are the most rated requirements. He said that the obtained results can be used for the preparation of conceptual design of plastic foldable chairs. Mohamad et al. (2017) have designed and produced a chair for postpartum mothers [5]. They studied the problem faced by them and prepared the house of quality based on their requirements. They found that most of the mothers wanted comfortable seat cushions (72 %), and comfort on countering (63.3 %). Other requirements most sought were easy to clean seat (61.1 %) and adjustable seat in height (31.7 %).

Rahman et al. (2018) have designed a weight measuring chair to be used by differently-abled persons, old men and small children who can't stand up on weight measuring device using house of quality [6]. They have designed chair based on important customer requirements from house of quality. Mukhtar (2019) have made the elongated chair using QFD technique [7]. He developed House of Quality using requirements of 15 different customers. They found that ergonomics was the most basic requirement of the customers with the highest score of 135.27. Wang et al. (2020) have developed the interactive design of an office chair using quality function deployment (QFD) and emotional design theory [8]. Using QFD approach and emotional concept, they found out the need of office chair users and integrated these finding in their new design. Zin et al. (2020) have analysed the feasibility of foldable chair which is

strapped onto the customer and can be used any where he wants [9]. They analysed customer requirements using house of quality method to design the chair.

In this paper, a relationship between customer requirements and engineering characteristics of a folding chair to be used by seamstresses working from their home have been analysed using house of quality. For that, a survey has been carried out to find out the important customer requirements. A relationship between requirements and different engineering qualities of a foldable chair is developed. Using house of quality, the most important engineering qualities of a folding chair have been found. At last, folding chair has been designed according to the requirement.

Methodology

Quality Function Deployment (QFD) is a team problem solving and a planning technique used by large number of industries to identify the customer requirements in the whole product development cycle. It was developed in Japan in the early 1970s and first used by Mitsubishi Heavy Industries. It was then adopted by many Japanese companies. After mid 1980s, many US companies used this method in defence, auto and electronics applications. It has been reported that 83% companies found increased customer satisfaction after QFD implementation.

In QFD, the term deployment refers to the fact that this method determines the important set of requirements for each phase of product development planning and uses them to identify the set of technical characteristics of each phase that most contribute to satisfying the customer requirements. QFD aides the design department in identifying the qualities of the elements in the product development phase and establishes a relationship between customers and the end product in each process. QFD is a group activity in which information is gathered by design team to solve the problems and to learn what about the solution. Because it is a process of making decision in a group, it creates a high level of brainstorming and understanding of the problem.

House of Quality (HoQ)

The QFD process has four phases which are product planning, part deployment, process planning and production planning. These phases of QFD are carried out in sequence and the output of each phase becomes input to the next phase. The first phase of the QFD is also called as House of Quality. It feeds results to the designing of individual parts of the product. From, the house of quality we can found out the important engineering characteristics required in the product. House of quality also provides the relationship between customer requirements and the features of the product. The HoQ converts requirements of customers in the quantifiable variable that is engineering characteristics. The HoQ can also be used for the identification of engineering characteristics which should be treated as constraints in designing the product and what should be the decision criteria in selecting the best conceptual design.

HoQ configuration has a total of eight rooms which are given bellow.

- (1) Room 1- Customer Requirements (Whats): In this room, customer requirements (CR) are listed by rows. CRs and its important rating can be found by surveys and team work (brainstorming). The importance rating may range from 1 to 5. CRs can be identify by asking questions in “whats” to the customers.
- (2) Room 2- Engineering Characteristics (Hows): ECs are the performance measures and features which are used for satisfying the ECs of the product. ECs can be measured. So, it has some units which are normally placed at the top of the room 2. ECs are found by asking questions in “Hows”.
- (3) Room 3- Correlation Matrix: This room shows the relationship between two engineering characteristics.
- (4) Room 4- Relationship Matrix (Whats related to hows): This room placed at the centre of the HoQ. It basically gives the relationship between customer requirements and engineering characteristics. If there is any relationship between a CRs and ECs then the cell connecting both the CRs and ECs will be filled with certain number from 1 to 9 in exponential way depending on the connection between the two.
- (5) Room 5- Importance Ranking: There are three rows in this room. Fist row is for absolute importance. It is calculated by fist multiplying the number given the cell of relationship matrix and customer importance rating. Then, the sum of the each column is placed in this row. Second row is for relative importance.
- (6) Room 6- Customer Assessment of Competing Products: In this room, competitors products are assessed though the customer rating given to them. This room provides information on the customer requirement which is most satisfied by others and which is not.
- (7) Room 7- Technical Assessment: In this room, assessment of complete product is carried out.
- (8) Room 8- Target Value: It is the end result of the HoQ.

User survey and problem analysis

The research work has been carried out using house of quality to find out the engineering characteristics a folding chair should possess which will be used by seamstresses. A survey has been carried out among the seamstresses, who sew in their home. The aim of the survey is to find out the important requirements of a folding chair. A total of 15 users mostly women were questioned and importance values of different customer requirements were averaged out.

The importance of requirements was analysed from the survey. The highly important user requirement was given 5 value and not much important demand was given 1 value. So, the all requirements were given values between 1 and 5 depending on its importance. The customer requirements were divided in to 4 groups which are convenience, safety and comfort, appearance and efficient. The broad classification is given in the Table. 1.

House of quality (HoQ) diagram for folding chair is prepared which is shown in the Fig.

1. The engineering characteristics of a folding chair, which are studied using house of quality, are structural design (mechanism for folding and unfolding), aesthetic appeals in seat and back, plasticity and elasticity of chair body, appropriate arc and angle of chair back, appropriate seat dimensions and contour, appropriate seat height, appropriate height back, parts can be disassembled and recycled, parts reduction, biodegradable material, weight, wear resistant, hardness, corrosion resistant and strength.

Table 1 Customer requirements and its importance

Group	Customer Requirement	Customer Importance
Convenience	Easy to fold and unfold	5
	Easy to transport	5
	Easy to store	5
	Easy to clean	2
Safety and comfort	Safe to use	2
	Comfortable seat	4
	Comfortable back	1
	Hand rest	1
Appearance	Surface finish	3
	Compact	4
	Aesthetic	1
Efficient	Reliability	4
	Serviceability	2
	Recycling and reuse	1

The relationship matrix between customer requirement and engineering characteristic has been established by filling the cell connecting the two. If the correlation between a requirement and a characteristic is higher, then the value 9 is placed in the cell. If the correlation is moderate and weak then 3 and 1 value are placed respectively. The correlation matrix at most upper part of the diagram indicates the relationship between two engineering characteristics. The absolute importance for an engineering characteristic has been calculated by multiplying the relationship number with customer importance value of the respective engineering characteristic and then summing them. Then, relative importance for an engineering characteristic is calculated by dividing absolute importance with total absolute importance and multiplying it with 100. After that engineering characteristics were ranked depending on its absolute importance.

Fig. 1. House of quality for a folding chair

Results and Analysis

There are number of engineering characteristics have been found for the foldable chair which can compensate the customer requirements. Among the engineering characteristics, the structural design (13 %) that is mechanism to fold the chair has highest absolute importance. The second most important engineering characteristic is weight (11.8 %) of the chair. So, the materials, which have lower density, should be selected. The manufacturer can use plastic or composite materials which have lower density. The importance of other engineering characteristic is: aesthetic appeals in seat and back (6 %), plasticity and elasticity of chair body (2.7 %), appropriate arc and angle of chair back (6.4 %), appropriate seat dimensions and contour (6.3 %), appropriate seat height (9.2 %), appropriate height back (9.2 %), parts can be disassembled and recycled (2.6 %), parts reduction (7.5 %), biodegradable material (5.3 %), wear resistant (7.5 %), hardness (2.2 %), corrosion resistant (3.9) and strength (5.5).

Convenience in using a chair is high priority for the user. The engineering characteristics which satisfy this demand most are structural design (mechanism of fold), parts minimization and weight. The engineering characteristics which fulfil the customer demand of comfort are design, contour, its dimensions and aesthetic appeals in the seat. The padding can be done on the seat or/and back of the chair. The seat and back height has higher absolute importance of 9.2 %. So, they should be optimized according to customer's demands. To improve the aesthetics of the chair corrosion and wear resistant material should be used. Also, contour and shape of the chair is chosen such that chair look beautiful. To improve serviceability and reliability of the chair, the engineering characteristics such as part reduction, easiness in assembling and disassembling the parts and strength of the chair material can help.

Design of the folding chair

Principle of manufacturing and assembly suggests that the product should have minimum number of components. It reduces the total assembly time, assembly cost, minimises the work-in progress and simplifies the automation. So, the chair has been designed such a way that it will have minimum number of components.

Based on the House of quality results the design of the folding chair has been prepared in the Autodesk Inventor software as show in the Fig. 2. As it can be seen in the figure there are total three major parts viz. part-1 with support, seat and part-2 as shown in Fig. 2a. In Fig. 2b, total of two cylindrical joints are shown. Under the seat, there is a wedge type support for part-2 to rest. As it has only two joint, it makes it easier to fold and unfold the chair. The dimensions of the seat will be 30×30 cm² and height from the floor will be 48 cm. The length of the back is 50 cm. The hand rest is not provided in the chair because it's lower customer requirement importance value.

Fig. 2. Design of the Folding chair in Autodesk Inventor software (a) Isometric view, (b) Side view and (c) View showing support under the seat

Material and manufacturing process selection

Materials and manufacturing process selected using Ashby's method [10]. There are total 3 major components in the chair. All the three components are subjected to bending. So, stiffness of the material is the most important property along with its density.

Functional Requirements: Light and stiff panel, Objectives: Minimize weight, and minimize cost, Constraints: Specified dimensions, Free variables: Choice of material

Fig. 3. Ashby material selection graph for the panel

Material index for a light and stiff panel is $M = E1/3/CRr$. So, it is required to maximize the $M2$. From the Fig. 3, the materials such as carbon steels, cast irons and Al alloys have been screened out. The material which is most suitable for the chair is aluminium alloy because the weight was the most important factor for the chair. For the manufacturing process selection also the Ashby's method has been used. Following are the important requirements for the manufacturing of the chair:

Functional Requirements: Shape an aluminium alloy, Objectives: Minimize cost, Constraints: Material Class: non-ferrous, Shape: 3D solid, Section thickness: 1.5 cm, Tolerance: 0.3 mm, Surface finish: 1 μ m, Planned batch size: 1000, Free variables: Choice of manufacturing process

From the set of constraints, the most suitable manufacturing process for the all three components is die-casting process.

Conclusion

This study has been carried out to find out which characteristics a folding chair should possess. For that a tool of quality function deployment, House of Quality has been used to find out the important engineering characteristics a folding chair for sewing worker. Results from the customer survey indicated that users want a chair which is convenient to use and the comfort was their second preference. It is found that mechanism of chair should be designed such that folding and unfolding of chair becomes easy. It is also argued that weight of the chair should be reduced at minimum.

From the input taken from the HoQ, a design of the folding chair is prepared which has three major components. From the Ashby graph, the most suitable material found for the chair is aluminium alloy; and the most suitable manufacturing process is the die casting process.

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